

**CONTRIBUTION OF TRIO: BHARATI MUKHERJEE, CHITRA BANERJEE
DIVAKARUNI AND OF MONICA ALI TO INDIAN WOMEN**

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Abstract

India has been a legendary country to worship women since ages and at the same time the country has been seeing destroyed position of women due to many factors. Outside invasions and cultural changes, arrogant patriarchal set-up increased misbehavior and cruelty and a rotten social structure had been started spreading as plague against female freedom, against female natural rights, against to accept females as an integral part of life without them. The present paper focuses not only on the struggle of feminist writers to give voice to the problems and issues of woman in Indian society but also on the emergence of the treatment of woman in Indian writing in English in the feminist and post-feminist era. Writers born and brought up in India, writing of Indian themes as well as writers of Diaspora have paid equal role to sustain credibility of feminism although they settle in alien land but pen for Indian and other South Asian land's women and about them. The purpose to showcase Bharati Mukherjee, Chitra Banerjee Divakaruni and of Monica Ali, the trio as forerunners of women's image and be a lighthouse to succeed on their path with hurdles. Their treatment of female protagonists has become a treasure for common women to move on in their lives in every the situation.

Keywords: Feminism, Women, Self-reliant, Identity, Messages, Patriarchal.

In Indian social milieu, the fact is globally accepted that woman is physically and emotionally equipped to perform equally with man. She has not only been denied to colonize as a complete human-being, but also deprived of the opportunities to give expression to her ideas, instincts and anguish. The woman, an inaudible bearer, is for ages waiting for emotional release. The function conveyed to man and to woman is one of the most structured patterns of Indian society. Woman is the follower, man the leader; woman is for the home, man of the world. Not only she has been defined as a subject in her authority but merely has an entity which deals with man either in his realistic or visionary life. Feminism is a serious attempt to formulate the issues and find solutions to gender problems. Feminist progression, started in 1960s in West went a mile-long route in arresting the injustice allocated to woman. Feminism, in universal phrase denotes the advocacy of woman's right to entire citizenship that encompasses financial and social equality with man. It is radically confronted phenomenon insofar as no general agreement exists about its boundaries. Believing on Simone de Beauvoir famous saying "One is not born, but rather becomes, woman." The trio has remarkably produced their characters to remember and to learn from them.

Bharati Mukherjee, a very popular name in Diaspora Literature has made a milestone for female identity. Her own reflection of strive in foreign land is visible in her female characters. She has given a way out to think about women an image with self-esteem that can be interpreted as self-image. An image and a person who faces ditches of gender, of a society, of a community, of a race and of a nation. Mukherjee has portrayed woman with the quest of ongoing journey where at a point she meets at least not all but satisfactory level of desired life for herself. While presenting Jasmine in *Jasmine*, Tara from *Tiger's Daughter* and in *Desirable Daughters*, Dimple in *Wife* and other protagonists from different novels i.e. *Holder of The World*, *Leave it to Me* etc. very well defined Indian women identity defined within the parameters of her social relationship to men. Indian women's identity is one that is usually connected to and defined by societal and cultural norms of a patriarchal familial structure. Bharati has demoted woman identity in different contexts, setting and

situation as being an independent decision maker, as an initiator to break orthodox rule in the name of morality that's a taboo on female's forehead.

Bharati's Tara in *The Tiger's Daughter* in 1972 is et about exposing how it feels for a young girl to leave a sheltered home, a fully grown young woman to come after breaking all social taboos by marrying a foreigner and see whether she can find a place at home again. She realizes that she could not communicate with that society simply because the society Tara rejoins is without a vision of the West. Bharati visualizes herself in Tara as after living so many years in Canada and America, when she visited Calcutta, her sound was found of a stranger to her native family and she was found stranger to everyone around them there. Mukherjee clearly paves way to Indian women to understand their stand and settle to a place and germ their own personality. It can be told confidently that no feminist writer is there who is not aware from the impact of character Jasmine, a tough survivor against all odds, faced by very few women to that extent but the way she discovers for herself being in more than one relation, as of widow, as of murderer and as of being victim of heinous rape, that's truly circulate an uncountable amount of courage for Indian women to fight in any worse situation and not to see themselves from the set eyes of the society, but they can be motivated all the while by themselves. A writer describes her so beautifully,

“As the female Brahma, she is her own creator, pregnant with new life; as a care giver, she matches Vishnu, the preserver, as Shiva's counterpart Kali, she has killed the demon, half-face, her rapist” (Tandon 160).

Dimple Dasgupta from 'Wife' is not a role model. It's a character conflicting between conventional traditions and modern, where she is drawn a character who ends in depression, madness and murder. The character is a great teaching to modern girls who dream to fly in artificial air of so called western culture without realizing its side effects. It's very vital to be rooted in our roots and balanced enough to live in any changed environment. Dimple's extreme madness can be taken as an effective case study for psychologists and medical neurosurgeons in context to personal and social contexts. The scene of killing her fetus is enough to tremble any sensible human.

“She hated the invisible mice for disrupting her day dreams. She stood up nervously and grabbed a broom as a weapon. She chased it behind the door...I'll get you? She screamed, “There's no way out of this, my friend? And in an outburst of hatred, her body shuddering, her wrist taut with fury, she smashed the top of a small gray head.... It had a strangely swollen body. A very small creature with a fat belly. To Dimple the dead mouse looked pregnant”(Tandon 47).

In the same manner Debbie or Devi from 'Leave it to Me' is also not liked much but a daughter of hybrid parent in America begins her search of biological mom, becomes a picaresque character from one city to another, seems quite challenging still for many Indian women, who are shy to come out from their own home even in twenty first century. Keeping aside the western factor of free culture for women, it's a need of time in our society also that every woman has to be self-independent in all major aspects of life. Tara from 'Desirable Daughters' sounds so similar as Indian women who are just living compromised and suffocating lives with husband against their wishes. Reason is not only domestic violence, Dowry, Greed, misbehavior but many a times no wit and emotional match creates complete vacuum that kills woman moment to moment and at a time she has to leave pressurized relation for mental peace. Tara messages same that women can be independent, marriage is not a compulsion and even females can begin new inning any time.

Chitra Banerjee Divakaruni is a popular award winning novelist and poet. Though she writes on a wide variety of themes, she directs much focus on the immigrant experience of the South Asian women in the U.S. She delineates the experiences and struggles involved in women trying to find their own identities. She is centrally concerned with giving shape to South Asian women's lives the United States. The combination of social concerns, hybridity, multiculturalism, immigration, racial intolerance, and “mystical realism,” are chief ingredients in Chitra's novels in special context to women. Chitra's narration with special treatment of themes and characters make them alive and of among us. Divakaruni has always been a lover of Indian mythology but not a blind follower. Being a sensible soul and creative writer she revives Draupadi from Mahabharata in *The Palace of Illusions*.

A complex character having innumerable controversies is presented remarkably as a daughter, as a sister, as a wife of five husbands, a friend of Krishana and appreciator of Karna in the fiction beyond her established image of a queen. The history is witness of an insult of a royal lady in the assembly of men before her husbands, whom she considered her pride.

Prathibha Ray, a great writer in Odisha and Jnapith award winner provides a psychological approach to the character of Draupadi. She vividly solaces with her in the lines, “Draupadi is a challenge of womanhood, the embodied form of action, knowledge, devotion and power. Such a woman – who has faced torment, insult, mental and emotional drama like Yajnaseni Draupadi – has not been born on this earth” (Suhana 728).

Draupadi is an excellent inspiration in all the eras to women to bear unexpected but never compromise with original self. If in classic age of restrictions over women, she could be such a bold and witty lady, why not today’s women can step out to fight against injustices happening with them.

Divakaruni’s *The Mistress of Spices* is about magic, wielded by a woman masquerading as an old and hunchbacked creature, but in reality, vibrant, eager for life, hungry with desires. Tilo, the protagonist of *Mistress of Spices*, has many guises and names that reveal her multiple identities. Chameleon-like, she keeps changing throughout the novel, making clear how complex the problem of identity crisis is that Indians try to cope in a foreign land. *Mistress of Spices* deals with the inner conflict raging within a woman who has to decide whether she has to live for the welfare of others or to live for herself. What she wants to tell to modern age women who are living in same dilemma to choose between personal and professional life, to choose between right and wrong, between to act or be silent and many such consequences, a woman has to learn to become a self-decision maker rather than depending on other family and social bodies for whole and sole decisions.

Bond between Sudha and Anju from *Sister of My Heart* defines value of virtues, worth of understanding and believe of righteous persons. Nothing can conquer ‘Love.’ It’s as natural as blood in the human body. The two sisters go beyond all their limits to save each other from all obstacles intentional, unintentional so intelligently. The whole world is crossing through the problem of hatred and disbelief in relations. For peaceful world, for peaceful life, it’s extremely important to believe on human values and on natural self, natural call. Chitra has imparted the message so strongly to women to practice and spread qualities and never bow before wrong practices. She says,

“Women in particular respond to my work because I’m writing about them, women in love, in difficulties, women in relationships, I want people to relate my characters, to feel their joy and pain, because it will be harder to (be) prejudiced when they meet them in real life” (Karthik 185).

Among the trio, the newest one is Monica Ali, a Bangladesh native, settled in Britain. Her debut novel *Brick Lane* gave her an immense popularity and award. Ali’s liberal point of view seeks to shed light on the predicament of less powerful members of non-Western cultures, such as women, who are oppressed by the customs and traditions of their cultures. By employing a liberal perspective, however, Ali not only oversimplifies the cultural concerns of the Bangladeshi immigrants in England but also reproduces a problematic and stereotypical picture of Bangladesh. Nazneen, a submissive woman of Bangladesh steps up to stay alone at the last of the novel in dream city London with two of her grown up daughters without support of husband, is a milestone for village and small town girls and women to imagine and live such a life. She develops courage to say NO to dictating and inhaling commandments of his orthodox husband who had made her life like a bird in cage. Similarly her sister Hasina goes beyond limitations of physical abuse, cheating in relation in personal life and observed deeply the condition of Islamic women working in factories, maids and as prostitutes. She gives a ray of hope to abandoned and cheated women to begin new phase as life gives more than one chance, it’s on she gender to pick it up to begin and evolve.

Ali's Untold Story is based on imaginary findings of the accidental death of very popular princess of Britain: princess Diana, whose demise is still controversial.

“This is the hypothesis that Monica Ali sets forth in her pot-boiler of a new novel, “Untold story” (Kakutani)

Like Chitra's Draupadi, she also exposes multifolded layers of royal lady Diana, who in her personal life suffered heartbreak and betrayal. Within a life of privilege, she frequently felt trapped and alone. Constrained by protocol and precedent, she refused to follow the rules. The messages of writers to common women are to live fair lives for themselves, where only they should be answerable for themselves. Women have to take their own responsibilities.

Women constitute about half of the world's population, but they share in various areas of activity which has been totally inconsistent with their numerical strength. History has revealed that men have always kept all substantial powers in their hands since the earliest days of the patriarchy. They have thought it best to keep women in a state of dependence and their codes of law have been set up against her and thus she has been definitely established as the other. Since then, women have always been considered as ‘weaker sex’ and they have been deprived of justice - social, economical, political and constitutional. They have often been marginalized and viewed as adjunct to men. Women are believed to bear children and caring them is their responsibility. In this way they are restricted to their homes and family roles.

All the three woman writers have made significant efforts to create identities of their own independent of any established theory. They all had firsthand experience in the alien soil. Being women, they were able to translate the experience of women with authenticity. In their portrayal of women, they have avoided the stereotypes. They have also highlighted the resilient nature of women which is a remarkable that facilitate women adapt themselves to circumstances better than men. The conventional portraits transnational women as victims have been broken, and these writers have projected them as champions who successfully overcome adverse circumstances.

Work Cited:

Dr. S. Karthikkumar, Dr.T.Karunakaran Women in Exile: ‘A Study of Chitra Banerjee Divakaruni, Bharati Mukherjee, and Anita Rau Badami’. Journal of Progressive Research in Social Sciences (JPRSS) Volume 3, Issue 2. 2016 ISSN: 2395-6283

Kakutani, Michiko. ‘Imagining A Secret Life For Diana’.New York Times. 13th June 2011.

P A, Suhana. “Acceptance, resistance and revenge Draupadi in Contemporary Indian Fiction.” International Journal of Applied Research 2017. ISSN 2394-7500.

Tandon, Sushma. Bharati Mukherjee's Fictions: A Perspective. Sarup & Sons, New Delhi. 2004.